
Health Status of Women In Sangli District (Maharashtra): A Geographical Study

Dr. Smt. S. M. Chavan¹ & Dr. Smt. A. B. Kamble²

¹Assistant Professor, Dept. of Geography,
Venutai Chavan College, Karad.

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Geography,
Art's & Commerce College, Kadepur.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Smt. S. M. Chavan

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15067464

Abstract:

The present paper deals with the accessibility of health care facilities to the people in general and to the women in particular in study region. In this paper highlighted the public health care policy in brief. In order to assess the access of health care facility the indices such as, female population per primary health care centre, female population per sub centre, public doctor population ratio, private doctor population ratio and distance of medical facilities etc. The present study based on the primary data. It has been also attempted to study the quality of public health care facility, government policy of public health care system and spatial distribution of these health care facilities in Sangli district.

Keywords: *Women Health, Female Population, Primary Health Center*

Introduction:

Access to health care facilities is one of the matters of great concern in India. The region disparities as well as imbalance in health care facilities especially public health care facilities are clearly observed in India. Some observation has been made in a health survey conducted in some rural areas of Maharashtra. The survey found, “Differential treatment is given to sick male and female children, in the sense that female are given free traditional treatment or do not receive any treatment, while treatment from qualified medical doctors is sought for male children” and in such scenario, if the public health centers are not available in nearby vicinity, the possibility of taking female child to medical practitioner reduces even further.

In this paper highlighted the public health care policy in brief. In order to assess the access of health care facility the indices

such as, female population per primary health care centre, female population per sub centre, public doctor population ratio, private doctor population ratio and distance of medical facilities etc. are taken into account for rigorous study. More precisely chapter has also focused on the manpower and infrastructure in public health care which has covered the tahsil wise number of ASHA and Nurses in Sangli district. In addition chapter has also focused on the service quality of health care facilities of private as well as public hospitals in the context of rural and urban area. The main focus of the present chapter is the health status of women in Sangli district. Hence firstly, the food habits and food stuff consumption pattern of women among the tahsils has been analyzed comprehensively. It has been also attempted to study the quality of public health care facility, government policy of public health care

system and spatial distribution of these health care facilities in Sangli district.

Objectives:

Now as per as the objectives of the present research is concern, to access the health care facilities by women and health status of women.

Choice of the Region:

In view of this the study region selected for present investigation is the Health status of women in Sangli District of Maharashtra state as a geography unit. Sangli District is having most favourable location in Maharashtra state. Sangli District is located into western part of Maharashtra between 16⁰45' to 17⁰ 33'N latitude and 73⁰42' E to 75⁰41' E longitude. District covers an area of 8572 Km² and it has population of 2820575 as per 2011 census.

Database and Methodology:

The present study based on the primary data of women health and necessary statistical tools such as percentile and graphs were applied for data processing purpose.

Results and Discussion:

Access to Health Care Facilities by Women:

Accessibility of the health care facilities to the remote places, downturn strata of the society and hilly area is always matter of concern in India. Especially, government health care services are not accessible to the rural mass due to various

like poor road connectivity, long distance, non-availability of doctors, poor medical infrastructure and bad perception of the peoples regarding public health care system.

Under this backdrop researcher is intended to study the regional disparities in the accessibility of the health care services in the context of rural -urban and public-private health care facilities. The accessibility of the health care facilities is measures through female population per primary health care centre, female population per sub centre, public doctor population ratio, private doctor population ratio and distance between respondent native places to health care centre.

Female Population per Primary Health Care:

The accessibility of health care facilities can be better understood with ratio of women population to primary health care center. It gives an idea about the population pressure on per primary health care centre. It also shows tahsil wise burden of population of the primary health care centers. In fact, the service quality of the primary health care centre is depends on the number of population served under the PHCs. More the population burden on PHC less will be the service quality and vice versa. Hence it has been attempted to study the average population per PHC in concern tahsil that has been calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Total population pressure per PHCs} = \frac{\text{Total population of the tehsil}}{\text{total number of PHCs in tehsil}}$$

$$\text{Women population pressure per PHCs} = \frac{\text{Total Women population of the tehsil}}{\text{total number of PHCs in tehsil}}$$

Table 1: Women Population per Primary Health Care

Sr. No	Tahsils	Population	No of PHC	Population per PHC	Women Population per PHC
1	Shirala	162911	7	23273	11725
2	Walwa	456002	11	41455	20077
3	Palus	164909	2	82455	39806
4	Kadegaon	143019	4	35755	17813
5	Khanapur	170214	3	56738	28530
6	Atpadi	138455	4	34614	17261
7	Tasgaon	251401	8	31425	15407
8	Miraj	854581	8	106823	52496
9	Kavatthe mahankal	152327	4	38082	18678
10	Jat	328324	8	41041	20009
Total		2822143	59	47833	23499

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 2016-17

The table 1. and fig. 1. shows population pressure per PHC and women population pressure per PHCs in Sangli district. It has been seen from the data that there are total 59 primary health care centers (PHCs) in Sangli district.

The maximum women population per PHCs has been observed to 52496 in Miraj tahsil and it has followed by Palus tahsil i.e 39806. It means that high women population pressure on PHCs has been observed in Miraj and Palus tahsil. Likewise, maximum total population per PHCs has been observed to 106823 in Miraj tahsil and it has followed by Palus tahsil i.e 41455. It means that high total population pressure on PHCs has been observed in Miraj and Palus tahsil.

The minimum population per PHCs has been observed in Shirala tahsil i.e 23273 and it has followed by Tasgaon i.e 31425. Moreover, the minimum women population per PHCs has been observed in Shirala tahsil i.e 11725 and it has followed by Tasgaon i.e 15407.

As per the government norms 2012, there should be 1 sub centre for per 5000 population in plain area and for per 3000 population in hilly and tribal area. There should be 1 primary health care centre for per 30000 populations in plain area and for per 20000 populations in hilly and tribal area. In addition, there should be 1 community health care centre for per 1, 20,000 population in plain area and for per 80,000 populations in hilly and tribal area.

The PHCs 35 are located in four tahsil namely Walwa, Tasgaon, Miraj and Jat. It means nearly 59 percent PHCs are concentrated in only these four tahsil. If we considered plain area norms then there should be 23 community Health Centers, 94 PHCs and 564 sub centers in the district. But the reality is different there are only 59 primary health care centers, 320 sub centers, and 3 community health care centers in the district. This gap indicates the low accessibility of public health care system in Sangli district.

Female Population per Sub Centre:

The sub centers are mainly working at grass root level. There are total 320 sub centers in Sangli district. Nearly 15.94 percent of the total sub centers are located in the Walwa tahsil followed by Shirala and Jat

by 13.13 percent. On the contrary the lowest percentage (i.e. 5.31 %) is observed in Palus followed by Atpadi (5.63%) and Kadegaon (5.63 %).

The table 2. Indicates the total population and women population per sub centre served in Sangli district. It has been seen from the data that the maximum women population per sub centre has been observed to 10768 in Miraj tahsil and it has followed by Palus tahsil i.e 4683. It means that high women population pressure on sub centre has been observed in Miraj and Palus tahsil. Likewise, maximum total population per sub centre has been observed to 21912 in Miraj tahsil and it has followed by Palus tahsil i.e 9701. It means that high total population pressure on sub centre has been observed in Miraj and Palus tahsil.

Table 2. Women Population per Sub Centre

Sr.No	Taluka	Population	No of Sub-centers	Population per Sub Centre	Women Population per Sub Centre
1	Shirala	162911	42	3879	1954
2	Walwa	456002	51	8941	4330
3	Palus	164909	17	9701	4683
4	Kadegaon	143019	18	7946	3958
5	Khanapur	170214	25	6809	3424
6	Atpadi	138455	18	7692	3836
7	Tasgaon	251401	34	7394	3625
8	Miraj	854581	39	21912	10768
9	Kavathe Mahankal	152327	34	4480	2197
10	Jat	328324	42	7817	3811
Total		2822143	320	8819	4333

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 2016-17

The minimum population per sub center has been observed in Shirala tahsil i.e 3879 and it has followed by Kavathemahankal i.e 4480. Moreover, the minimum women population per sub center has been observed in Shirala tahsil i.e 1954 and Kavathemahankal i.e 2197.

In short, Shirala and Kavathemahankal tahsil are having low population as well as women population pressure and on the contrary the Miraj and Palus tahsil are having high population as well as women pressure. It indicates not only the population pressure but also the burden on medical infrastructure and hampers to the quality of service to them. Even the minimum pressure is also significantly more in both PHCs as well as sub centers as per the government norms.

Public Doctor Population Ratio:

Doctors those are serve in government sector is known as public doctor. The national density of doctors was 79.7 per lakh population, of nurses and midwives 61.3 per lakh, and of dentists just 2.4 per lakh. There were 12, 25, 381 health workers in urban areas and 8,44,159 in rural areas, an urban–rural ratio of 1.45. Of all health workers, 59.2% were in urban areas,

where 27.8% of the population resides, and 40.8% were in rural areas, where 72.2% of the population resides. The ratio of urban density to rural density for doctors was 3.8, for nurses and midwives 4.0, and for dentists 9.9.

The doctor-population ratio of the some of the countries are: Australia 3.374:1000, Brazil 1.852:1000, China 1.49:1000, France 3.227:1000, Germany 4.125:1000, Russia 3.306:1000, the USA 2.554:1000, Afghanistan 0.304:1000, Bangladesh 0.389:1000, Pakistan 0.806:1000. Whereas it is just 0.62 : 1000 in India

Under this overall backdrop, researcher has attempted to study the public doctor population ratio as well as private doctor population ratio in Sangli district.

The table 3 and fig. 3 indicates tahsil wise average population and women population served by per one public doctor in Sangli district. There are total 420 public doctors operating in 10 tahsils of Sangli district. The maximum i.e 241 (more than 50 per cent) is working in Miraj tahsil. It implies greater degree of disparities in the spatial distribution number of public doctors in study region.

Table 3: Population and Women Population per Public Doctor

Sr.No	Tahsils	Public Doctor	Population per Public Doctor	Women Population per Public Doctor
1	Shirala	22	7405	3731
2	Walwa	34	13412	6495
3	Palus	8	20614	9951
4	Kadegaon	16	8939	4453
5	Khanapur	14	12158	6114
6	Atpadi	12	11538	5754
7	Tasgaon	33	7618	3735
8	Miraj	241	3546	1743
9	Kavathe Mahankal	16	9520	4670
10	Jat	24	13680	6670
Total		420	6719	3301

Source: Socio-economic abstract of Sangli district ,2016-17

The data reveals the fact that maximum average population i.e 20614 is being served by one doctor in Palus tahsil. The maximum average women population i.e 9951 is being served by one doctor in Palus tahsil.

Minimum average population i.e 3546 is being served by one doctor in Miraj tahsil. The minimum average women population i.e 1743 is being served by one doctor in Miraj tahsil. In short, it can be stated that the public doctors are mainly working in Miraj tahsil and other tahsils are suffering from the chronic shortage of public doctors.

Private Doctor Population Ratio:

Along with the public doctors there are private doctors who serve people in rural as well as urban area. In fact, it is a private doctor and private hospital where middle class and upper middle class families prefer to visit rather than public hospital. Hence it is also necessary to get an idea about the population and women population per private doctor in study region.

It has been evidence from the data presented in table 4. and fig. 4. that there are total 1785 private doctors practicing in Sangli district, out of which 834 (46.72 per cent of the total district private doctors) are practicing in Miraj tahsil alone. No doubt, the Miraj city is emerging as a medical hub in Sangli district but 46 per cent doctor's agglomeration in one place of the district is

not appreciable in geographical point of view. It indicates sharp disparities in the medical accessibility in Sangli district. The 1344 (75.29 per cent) out of 1785 private doctors are just practicing in five tahsils namely Miraj, Jat, Tasgaon, Walwa and Shirala. In other words only 25 per cent of the total private doctors are practicing in reaming five tahsils (or 50 per cent of the tahsils). It also indicates acute disparities in health care access in Sangli district. In other words there is imbalance in availability of private doctors in Sangli district.

It has been seen from the table 4. and fig. 4. that high population i.e 2985 and high women population i.e 1455 per private doctor is being served in Jat tahsil. It has followed by Walwa tahsil i.e 2682 population per private doctor and 1299 women population per private doctor.

Low population i.e 1025 and low women population i.e 504 per private doctor is being served in Miraj tahsil. It has followed by Shirala tahsil i.e 1481 population per private doctor and 746 women population per private doctor. At district aggregate level 1581 people is being served by one private doctor in Sangli district. Likewise, one private doctor served 777 women in Sangli district.

In short, there is low accessibility of health care facilities except Miraj tahsil in Sangli district in terms of number of public and private doctors.

Table 4: Population and Women Population per Private Doctor

Sr.No	Tahsils	Private Doctor	Population per Private Doctor	Women Population per Private Doctor
1	Shirala	110	1481	746
2	Walwa	170	2682	1299
3	Palus	85	1940	937
4	Kadegaon	92	1555	774
5	Khanapur	88	1934	973
6	Atpadi	80	1731	863
7	Tasgaon	120	2095	1027
8	Miraj	834	1025	504
9	Kavathe Mahankal	96	1587	778
10	Jat	110	2985	1455
	Total	1785	1581	777

Source: Socio-economic abstract of Sangli district, 2016-17

Distance of Medical Facilities:

The distance between residential place to health care facilities are also matter in spatial variations in access to health care facilities. The near the health care facilities from residential place indicates good accessibility and vice versa. In fact, distance is matter at the time of medical emergency. The table 5. indicates distance between residential places to medical facilities. Here the term medical facilities includes any of the facilities such as medical, hospital, clinic, PHCs, Sub – centre etc. It has been evidence from the data that 75 per cent respondents of Shirala tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place.

The 5 per cent respondents of Shirala tahsil were said that medical facility is made available at less than 1 Km. The 10 per cent respondents said that medical facility is made available at 1 to 2 Km. The 5 per cent respondents said that 2 to 5 km is the distance between their residential place to medical facilities and remaining 5 per cent respondent women were reported that there is more than 5 Km distance between health care facility and their residential place.

The 63.6 per cent respondents of Walwa tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place.

Table 5: Distances of Medical Facilities from Native Place of Respondents (In Percentage)

Sr.No	Tahsils	Percentage of Respondents				
		Near the Premises of Native Place	Less than 1 km	Up to 1 to 2 Km	2 to 5 Km	More than 5 Km
1	Shirala	75	5	10	5	5
2	Walwa	63.6	0	4.5	9.1	22.7
3	Palus	18.8	68.8	6.3	0	6.3
4	Kadegaon	00	26.7	13.2	0	60.0
5	Khanapur	6.3	87.7	0	6.3	6.3
6	Atpadi	42.9	21.4	28.6	0	7.1
7	Tasgaon	58.3	8.3	25.0	8.3	0
8	Miraj	66.7	20.0	11.1	2.2	0
9	Kavathe Mahankal	62.5	12.5	25.0	0	0
10	Jat	46.2	0	0	30.8	23.1
Total		44.03	25.04	12.37	6.17	13.05

Source: Field Work, 2016

The only 18.8 per cent respondents of Palus tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place.

The remaining 60.0 per cent women respondent were reported that there is more than 5 Km distance between health care facility and their residential place in Kadegaon.

The 6.3 per cent respondents of Khanapur tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place.

The 42.9 per cent respondents of Atpadi tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place

The 58.3 per cent respondents of Tasgaon tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place. The 8.3 per cent respondents said that medical facility is made available at less than 1 Km. The 25 per cent respondents said that 1to 2 km is the distance between their residential place to medical facilities and remaining 8.3 per cent respondent women were reported that there is 2 to 5 Km distance between

health care facility and their residential place in Tasgaon.

The 66.7 per cent respondents of Miraj tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place. The 20 per cent respondents said that medical facility is made available at less than 1 Km. The 11.1 per cent respondents said that 1to 2 km is the distance between their residential place to medical facilities and remaining 2.2 per cent respondent women were reported that there is 2 to 5 Km distance between health care facility and their residential place in Miraj.

The 62.5 per cent respondents of Kavathe Mahankal tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place. The 12.5 per cent respondents said that medical facility is made available at less than 1 Km. the 25 per cent respondents said that 1to 2 km is the distance between their residential place to medical facilities.

The 46.2 per cent respondents of Jat tahsil are having medical facilities near the premises of residential place. The 30.8 per

cent respondents said that medical facility is made available at 2 to 5 Km. The remaining 23.1 per cent respondent women were reported that there is more than 5 Km distance between health care facility and their residential place in Jat tahsil.

Another reason behind service quality gap between private and public hospitals is the control over medical resources and decision making power. In private hospital sole decision were taken by owner of the hospital and in public hospitals government takes decision. The control over resources is partial in public hospital and it is full control in private hospitals.

Health Status of Women:

To study the health status of women in geographical perspective is one of the core objectives of the present research task. It has been widely discussed with the help of different components such as food habits and food Stuff consumption pattern, timely meal, breakfast habits, frequency of illness, nature and extent of water born diseases, other diseases, awareness about health, negligence of health issues and respondents opinion about their health status.

Conclusion:

The present research has mainly focused on the accessibility of health care facilities to the people in general and women population of Sangli district in particular. It has been clear from the analysis that most of the medical facilities are concentrated in Miraj tahsil and other tahsils are being neglected. There is totally uneven spatial

distribution of various medical facilities in Sangli district. The urban – rural health access gap is widening in Sangli district. The health status of women in Sangli district is matter of great concern, so far as deficit food stuff consumption is concern. Moreover, spatial distribution of health status is also significantly differs in Sangli district.

References:

1. Caraballo H (2014), Emergency department management of mosquito-borne illness: Malaria, dengue, and west Nile virus. *Emergency Medicine Practice*. 16 (5). Archived from the original on 2016-08-01.
2. Directorate of Economics and Statistics (2017), *Socio-Economic Review of Sangli District 2017*
3. Madhev G Deo(2013), Doctor population ratio for India - The reality, *Indian Journal of Medical Research IJMR*, April 137 issue 4 pp. 632-635
4. Sudhir Anand and Victoria Fan (2016), *The Health Workforce in India, Human Resource for Health Observer Series No. 16*, World Health Organization, Publication, WHO Document Production Services, Geneva, Switzerland.
5. Swarn Lata Sakhuja (2008), *The Medical And Health Care Of Women, A Sociological Study of Rural and Tribal Hilly Area of Uttaranchal Pradesh*, Gyan Publishing House, New Delhi.